

Organic Ion-exchange Beads as Indicator in Acid-Base Titration

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Manuscript received 25 March 1985, accepted 29 October 1985

Phosphorylated ion-exchanger was prepared by a new method where the resin can change its colour according to pH of the medium. The resin was used as indicator in direct acid-base titration, both in aqueous and aqueous organic media. A comparison was made between the synthesised resin indicator and other available indicators. Slight deviation was found in the results. The optimum pH range for the function of the resin as indicator was found to be 8-10.

THERE are many applications of ion-exchange resins in analytical chemistry in both quantitative and qualitative analysis. Ion-exchange resins have been used for the detection of esters¹, amides, imides, anilides², nitriles³, aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes⁴, respectively are also used for the determination of aliphatic unsaturated amides and esters⁵. The resin spot technique was first developed by Fujimotu⁶ in the detection of microgram of compounds. The test has been successfully employed for simultaneous detection of nitrogen, sulphur, chlorine, and iodine when they are present in microgram amounts in the given organic mixture. Resin beads loaded with indicators have also been used for the titration of acids and bases^{7,8}. Honda⁹ used such resin beads to estimate pH in the resin phase. Qureshi *et al.*¹⁰ used resin beads in Fe²⁺ or *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodamine form as indicator in precipitation titrations with potassium ferrocyanide. Rawat and Thind¹¹ showed that ferric phosphate inorganic ion-exchangers can be used as indicators. Thind and Sandue¹² used ferric phosphate inorganic ion-exchanger also for the determination of various ions in pure form and in presence of other ions.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile-, butadiene-, styrene copolymer (ABS) (Ugikral-SN-France) was used as substrate for synthesising the cation-exchanger. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Synthesis: Phosphoric acid cation-exchange resin was prepared by phosphorisation of ABS crosslinked with phenol-formaldehyde resin (resol). In a three-necked flask, ABS copolymer (45 g) was dissolved in benzene (150 ml) at 70°, the crosslinking agent (5 g) was then added to the polymer emulsion with continuous stirring till complete homogeneous solution was obtained. The blended polymer was

obtained after evaporating the solvent at room temperature. Phosphorylated ion-exchanger was prepared by refluxing the crosslinked polymer for 8 h with PCl₅, using anhydrous AlCl₃ as a catalyst. The resulting product was hydrolyzed in ice-water¹³⁻¹⁷. Various concentrations of nitric acid (0.1-0.5 M) were used to oxidise the phosphonic acid group to phosphonic group, and the reaction time was 3 h. The validity of each experiment was tested by observing the colour change after immersion in 0.5 N sodium hydroxide solution for 24 h at room temperature. The optimum concentration of nitric acid is 0.2 M, and the ion-exchange capacity is 1.31 meq/g dry resin. The capacity of the phosphorylated resins were determined by two methods:

(i) *Direct titration:* In order to know the number of exchangeable hydrogen ions at different dissociation stages, various salts of weak acids were used. Data observed in Table 1 shows an increase in the exchange capacity with increasing pH of the solution indicating the presence of 'weak acid' capacity.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTALLY DETERMINED CAPACITIES AT
VARIOUS pH VALUES

pH	capacity dry resin meq/g
6.8	0.51
9.0	0.99
10.3	1.12
12.7	1.31

(ii) *Potentiometric titration curves:* The procedure involves an addition of a salt of a weak acid to the resin, and determining the pH of the equilibrated solution. The titration showed an

Fig. 1. Ir spectrum of resin indicator : (a) before oxidation and (b) after oxidation.

increase in the pH of the solution with increasing milliequivalents of the added alkali. The titration curve of ion-exchange resin showed one distinct inflection and two very small inflections. Hence, it appears to be a tribasic acid. The first ionisation occurs at a pH slightly higher than that of sulphonic acid resin, while the second and third groups are at a pH intermediate between the carboxylic and phenolic types. Table 2 shows the pK values of the OH groups and the dissociation constants of the studied resin.

TABLE 2

pK_a value	Dissociation constant
$pK_1 = 2.192$	$k_1 = 1.523 \times 10^{-11}$
$pK_2 = 4.900$	$k_2 = 5.012 \times 10^{-7}$
$pK_3 = 7.199$	$k_3 = 3.980 \times 10^{-12}$

Elemental analysis of the synthesised resin is : C, 60.12 ; O, 17.54 ; N, 5.91 ; H, 7.27 ; P, 6.16%. The ir spectrum of the resin before and after oxidation are recorded in Fig. 1. For phosphonic resin (Fig. 1b), the P=O stretching frequencies can be identified in the hydrogen form as a broad band at $\sim 1180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating considerable H-bonding. Symmetrical absorption of PH_2 is shown at $\sim 1070 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The usual aromatic absorption is present, in both the curves, and some carboxylic peaks appear as a result of the oxidation process. The acid resins, for example, show similar but slightly lower $\nu_{\text{P=O}}$ (Fig. 1a).

The stability studies of the phosphonated resin after oxidation against several treatments showed that the loss in the capacity is 2.29% on treatment with 2 N NaOH solution for 2 days. On treatment with 2 N HNO_3 , the loss in the capacity is 4.58%. However, treatment with common organic solvents had negligible effect on the original capacity. Boiling the resin with water for 10 h decreased the

capacity to 3.05%. Heating the resin in an oven at 150° for 16 h results in a decrease in the capacity to 2.29%.

Preparation of K-form of phosphonated resin : The cation exchanger (1 g) was soaked in 1 M KCl for 3 h. The resin was rinsed with deionised water and air-dried. Similar methods were used for preparing the resins in Li and Na forms.

Titration method by cation-exchanger in aqueous media :

Reagents : The phosphonated cation-exchanger ($\sim 15 \text{ mg}$) in H, K-forms, 0.1 N HCl (standard) and 0.1 N NaOH (unknown), were used.

Procedure : (i) Sodium hydroxide (25 ml) solution was transferred with pipette to a conical flask. Add the phosphonated cation-exchanger (15 mg) in the H-form was added to the solution (the colour of the resin changed from white-green to orange-red immediately on addition of sodium hydroxide. (ii) The acid was added from the burette gradually with continuous stirring of the solution using a magnetic stirrer. Near the end point, the colour changed to pale green. The acid was then added dropwise till the colour of the resin changed from pale green to white-green. (iii) The previous experiment was repeated with the other forms of resin. (iv) Steps (i) to (iii) were repeated reversing the position of both the acid and alkali.

The same procedures were repeated in the presence of different indicators, thymolphthalein, phenolphthalein, bromthymol blue and methyl orange.

Titration method by cation-exchanger in aqueous-organic medium :

Reagents : The phosphonated cation exchanger ($\sim 15 \text{ mg}$) in H- and K-forms ; 0.1 N HCl

(standard), 0.1 N NaOH (unknown), ethanol, acetone and dioxane were used.

Procedure: The same procedure was repeated as in the aqueous media, after addition of 25 ml of the organic solvent to the conical flask containing the resin.

Discussion

Calculation of the percentage deviation: The deviation percentage is calculated according to the following relation,

$$\% \text{Deviation } (\pm) = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Equivalent volume of the titre}}{\text{Equivalent volume of the titre}} \right)_{S.I.} - \left(\frac{\text{Equivalent volume of the titre}}{\text{Equivalent volume of the titre}} \right)_{R.I.}}{\left(\frac{\text{Equivalent volume of the titre}}{\text{Equivalent volume of the titre}} \right)_{S.I.}} \times 100$$

where, S.I. refers to the standard indicators used and R.I. means the resin indicator.

In the present work, we report the validity of the synthetic resin as indicator in acid-base titration. These studies involve the neutralisation of strong acid by a strong base in aqueous and aqueous organic solvent. The analytical data observed in presence of resin indicator compared with the corresponding values using various types of standard indicators, viz. thymolphthalein, phenolphthalein, bromthymol blue and methyl orange. The phosphonated cation exchanger is used in different ionic forms, i.e. H⁺ and K⁺. The percentage deviation with different forms of resin was calculated. Titration experiments were conducted in aqueous solution with both the resin and

standard indicators (Table 3). Converting the resin indicator to the K-form with the same previous conditions, results in a smaller positive deviation in the analytical data than those obtained using the resin in hydrogen form. Such smaller deviations are obtained with thymolphthalein indicator. Higher magnitudes of deviation are given with methyl-orange indicator.

In general, it has been found that in aqueous media the percentage deviation decreases with increasing pH range of the standard indicator,

whereas it decreases in presence of resin in K-form with acid as titrant or the H-form of resin with alkali as titrant. In aqueous organic medium, the cations tend to migrate from solution phase to the resin phase¹⁸ and hence there is a marked change in the calculated values of deviation using the resin either in H-form or in Li-, Na- and K-forms.

From the foregoing discussion, it is clear that the synthetic cation-exchanger can be used as indicator in both aqueous and aqueous organic media.

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TABLE 3—CALCULATED PERCENTAGE DEVIATION FOR ANALYTICAL DATA IN PRESENCE OF RESIN INDICATOR FROM THOSE VALUES OBTAINED USING STANDARD INDICATORS

Working medium	Standard indicator* (pH)	Ionic form of resin indicator	% deviation	
			Resin + HCl	Resin + NaOH
H ₂ O	Thymol. (9.3-10.5)	H ⁺	-1.011	+0.511
		K ⁺	+0.432	-0.911
EtOH-H ₂ O 50% (v/v)		H ⁺	-1.121	+0.723
		K ⁺	+0.331	-0.823
H ₂ O	Phenol. (8.3-10)	H ⁺	-1.221	+0.799
		K ⁺	+0.621	-1.211
EtOH-H ₂ O 50% (v/v)		H ⁺	-1.232	+0.992
		K ⁺	+0.532	-0.999
H ₂ O	Brom. (6.0-7.6)	H ⁺	-1.428	+1.332
		K ⁺	+0.823	-1.511
EtOH-H ₂ O 50% (v/v)		H ⁺	-1.571	+1.324
		K ⁺	+0.777	-1.323
H ₂ O	Methyl. (3.1-4.4)	H ⁺	-1.611	+1.562
		K ⁺	+1.011	-1.792
EtOH-H ₂ O 50% (v/v)		H ⁺	-1.811	+1.723
		K ⁺	+0.992	-1.623

*Thymol, = Thymolphthalein, Phenol. = phenolphthalein
Brom. = bromothymol blue, Methyl. = methyl orange.